

Synthesis of some New Pyridazinonyl, Naphthyl and Benzofluorenyl Derivatives via Stobbe Condensation Reaction

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In continuation of our studies¹ on Stobbe reaction we have synthesised some pyridazinonyl, naphthyl and benzofluorenyl derivatives.

4-Chloro-3-methylacetophenone was condensed with diethylcyclohex-1-enyl succinate in the presence of potassium t-butoxide under Stobbe condensation conditions²⁻⁴ to give a crude half-ester *trans*-(4-Cl-3-Me/COOEt)-2-cyclohex-4-(4-chlorotolyl)buten-3-oic acid (1) which on saponification gave an acid (2) (Scheme 1). The acid (2) on reacting with acetyl chloride formed the acid anhydride (3) which on hydrolysis¹ gave 4. The reaction of 4 with hydrazine hydrate⁵ gave 5-chloro-1,6-dimethyl[2,3-*b*]indeno-4-(cyclohex-1-enyl)pyridazin-3(2*H*)-one (5). Cyclisation of the dibasic acid (2) with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride gave compound 6 and the acid 7 (Scheme 2). Alkylation of 7² with dimethyl sulphate and/or ethyl chloroacetate gave 8a and 8b. Reaction of the ester (8b) with hydrazine hydrate and phenylhydrazine gave 10a,b which upon saponification with 10% aqueous NaOH gave 9a,b. Treatment of 9a with phosphoric oxide⁶ in dry ben-

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

zene gave 11 which was reacted with hydrazine hydrate and/or phenylhydrazine giving the corresponding benzofluorenone hydrazones (12a,b).

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. Ir (KBr) spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicam spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO) on a Varian VN (90 Mz) instrument.

4-Cl-3-Me/COOEt)-2-cyclohex-4-(4-chlorotolyl)buten-3-oic acid (1) : A mixture of 4-chloro-3-methylaceto-

phenone (1 mol) and diethylcyclohex-1-enyl succinate (1 mol) was added dropwise to a gently warmed solution of potassium t-butoxide and the mixture was stirred for 2 h on a water-bath. It was then slightly acidified with dilute HCl and the concentrated residual product was dissolved in cold water. The oily product was extracted with ether, the ethereal layer extracted with 10% aqueous Na_2CO_3 , acidified with ice-cold dilute HCl and oily mass extracted with ether. Evaporation of the dried ethereal extract gave the crude oily product (60%).

trans-(4-Cl-3-Me/COOH)-2-cyclohex-1-enyl-3-carboxy-4-(4-chlorotolyl)-buten-3-oic acid (2): The oily half-ester (**1**; 30 g) was refluxed with 10% aqueous NaOH for 5 h. The cold alkaline solution was acidified with dilute HCl, the solid extracted with ether, then acidified with ice-cold dilute HCl, and the resulting solid was crystallised from benzene, (65%), m.p. 163°; ν_{max} 1 690 and 1 720 cm^{-1} (conjugated and nonconjugated C=O respectively).

The cyclic anhydride (3): The dibasic acid (**2**; 6 g) was refluxed with acetyl chloride (60 ml) for 2 h. The excess acetyl chloride was then removed by distillation, the last traces being removed by addition of small amount of light petrol (b.p. 60–80°) followed by distillation to give the product which was dried and crystallised from benzene, (60%), m.p. 85°.

3-Oxo-5-chloro-1,6-dimethyl-2-indenylcyclohex-1-enyl-acetic acid (4): To a stirred ice-cold solution of the anhydride (**3**; 5 g) in acetylene tetrachloride (50 ml), anhydrous AlCl_3 (5 g) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred on a water-bath for 2 h and left aside for 2 days at room temperature, then decomposed with ice-cold dilute HCl. The excess acetylene tetrachloride was removed by steam distillation and the product was extracted with 5% aqueous Na_2CO_3 . The cold alkaline solution was acidified with ice-cold dilute HCl to give the product which was dried and crystallised from benzene, (60%) m.p. 215°; ν_{max} 1 705, 1 685 cm^{-1} ; δ 2.2 (6H, 2 \times CH_3), 2.6 (1H, s, CH aliph), 2.8–3.0 (8H, m, 4 \times CH_2 cyclic), 6.3–6.6 (3H, m, ArH).

5-Chloro-1,6-dimethyl-[2,3-b]-indeno-(4-cyclo-1-enyl)-pyridazin-3(2H)-one (5): A mixture of the indenylacetic acid derivative (**4**; 0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) was refluxed in n-butanol (60 ml) for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated and cooled to give the product which was dried and crystallised from toluene, (55%), m.p. 265°; ν_{max} 3 450 (OH), 3 230 (NH), 1 680 (C=O), 1 630 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ 2.3 (6H, s, 2 \times CH_3), 2.7–2.9 (8H, m, 4 \times CH_2 cyclic), 6.1–6.8 (2H, m, ArH), 8.5 (1H, s, NH).

Ethyl 4-acetoxy-3-cyclohex-1-enyl-6-chloro-1,7-dimethylnaphthoate (6): A mixture of the half-ester (**1**; 15 g), fused sodium acetate (5 g) and acetic anhydride (100 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. The excess acetic anhydride was removed under reduced pressure, then water was added and the

aromatic material was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, dried and evaporated to give the product.

The naphthoic acid derivative (7): The acetoxy naphthoate (**6**; 5 g) was refluxed with 10% aqueous NaOH (70 ml) for 5 h and the solution extracted with ether to remove the unsaponified material. The alkaline solution was then cooled, acidified with dilute HCl and the resulting solid was extracted with ether. Evaporation of the dried ethereal layer gave the product which was dried and crystallised from toluene, (55%), m.p. 210; ν_{max} 1 750 (C=O), 3 350 cm^{-1} (OH).

Methyl 4-methoxy-3-cyclohex-1-enyl-6-chloro-1,7-dimethyl-2-naphthoate (8a) and 4-ethoxycarbonylmethoxy-6-chloro-1,7-dimethyl-3-cyclohex-1-enyl-2-ethoxycarbonylmethyl-2-naphthoate (8b): A mixture of the naphthoic acid (**7**; 0.01 mol) and each of dimethyl sulphate and ethyl chloroacetate in dry acetone using anhydrous K_2CO_3 as a catalyst, was refluxed for 20 h, the excess acetone was then evaporated under reduced pressure and water (100 ml) added. The organic material was extracted with ether and the dried ethereal layer was evaporated to yield the esters (**8a,b**) which were crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°): **8a** (65%), m.p. 135° and **8b** (63%), 115°; ν_{max} 1 720 cm^{-1} (C=O ester); δ 1.3 (6H, t, 2 \times CH_2CH_3), 2.2 (6H, s, 2 \times CH_3 attached to aromatic), 4.5 (4H, s, 2 \times CH_2CO), 2.8–3.0 (8H, m, 2 \times CH_2 cyclic), 3.5 (4H, q, CH_2CH_3), 6.6–6.8 (2H, m, ArH).

Saponification of the ester (8a,b) to (9a,b): These were prepared as the formation of compounds **2** and **7**: **9a** (60%), m.p. 185°; **9b** (50%), 208°.

The hydrazides (10a,b): A mixture of the ester (**8b**; 0.01 mol) and hydrazines, namely, hydrazine hydrate and/or phenylhydrazine (0.01 mol) was refluxed in butanol (50 ml) for 5 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated, the solid separated was dried and crystallised from ethanol: **10a** (65%), m.p. 241°; **10b** (63%), 223°.

6-Chloro-7,9-dimethyl-4-methoxy[2,3-b]benzofluoren-1-(2H)-one (11) and the hydrazone derivatives (12a,b): A solution of the acid (**10a**; 1.5 g) in dry benzene (20 ml) and P_2O_5 (10 g) was refluxed for 3 h. The excess benzene was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue was cooled and decomposed with water. The oily product was extracted with ether and washed with Na_2CO_3 solution. The dried ethereal layer was evaporated to give the oily product of benzofluorenone (**11**) which on refluxing with each of hydrazine hydrate and phenylhydrazine (0.01 mol) in ethanol for 5 h gave the corresponding hydrazone derivatives which were crystallised from ethanol: **12a** (58%), m.p. 153°, ν_{max} 1 660 cm^{-1} (C=N), δ 3.5 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.5 (6H, s, 2 \times CH_3), 2.8–3.1, (8H, m, 4 \times CH_2 cyclic), 6.5–7.0 (7H, m, ArH), 9.5 (1H, s, NH); **12b** (55%), 143°.

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